

Solitary Metastatic Destruction of the Left Sternoclavicular Joint in a Patient with Triple-Negative Breast Cancer: A Case Report & Review of literature

Dr. M. A. Naseer ^{*1}, Dr Gagan Deep Singh ², Mr. Prashant Patiyal ³, Dr Ansar ⁴

1. Department of Radiation Oncology, Surjit Multispecialty & Cancer Hospital, Amritsar, Punjab.

2,3,4. Surjit Multi Speciality and Cancer Hospital.

***Correspondence to:** Dr. M. A. Naseer, Department of Radiation Oncology, Surjit Multispecialty & Cancer Hospital, Amritsar, Punjab.

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Abstract

Background: Solitary metastasis to the sternoclavicular joint (SCJ) is an exceedingly rare presentation of breast cancer. Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) is known for its aggressive biology and early recurrence.

Case Presentation: A 50-year-old female with treated pT2pN1Mx right-sided TNBC presented 16 months post-surgery with a suprasternal swelling. Imaging (CE-CT/PET- CT) revealed a solitary, FDG-avid lytic destructive lesion of the left manubrium and clavicular head with soft tissue swelling over the bone. Despite inconclusive biopsy, clinical history led to the diagnosis of solitary bone metastasis.

Conclusion: Isolated SCJ involvement in TNBC is very rare and mimics localized inflammatory conditions. Clinicians should maintain high degree of suspicion for unusual bony recurrences in TNBC, which require localized palliative radiotherapy for skeletal stability & good pain control.

Keywords: Triple-negative breast cancer, sternoclavicular joint, bone metastasis, lytic lesion, palliative radiotherapy.

Introduction

Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) lacks estrogen, progesterone, and HER-2 receptor expression, correlating with high recurrence rates and poor prognosis[1, 2, 3]. While bone is a frequent site for breast cancer metastasis, the sternoclavicular joint (SCJ) is rarely involved in isolation (<5%) [4]. We present a unique case of metachronous solitary lytic metastasis to the contralateral SCJ following standard multimodal treatment for TNBC.

Case Presentation

A 50-year-old female was diagnosed with invasive ductal carcinoma of the right breast in August 2024. She underwent breast-conserving surgery (BCS) and axillary lymph node dissection. The pathology revealed 2.5x2x2cm, grade 2 triple negative breast cancer. 2/12 axillary lymph nodes were involved. She received dose dense adjuvant chemotherapy AC followed by Docetaxel completed in March 2025. This was followed by adjuvant VMAT radiotherapy to the right breast/SCF (45 Gy/25 fractions) with a 12 Gy boost, completed in May 2025.

The patient presented in December 2025, with a palpable, firm suprasternal swelling. CE-CT on December 27 revealed lytic destruction of the manubrium sternum and left clavicular head with an associated soft tissue mass (Image 1). PET-CT (December 29) showed no systemic disease except for an FDG-avid destructive lesion at the left SCJ and 1st left costo-chondral junction (Image 2).

FNAC and core biopsy were performed but remained inconclusive due to the dense stromal reaction. Based on the aggressive clinical history and radiographic evidence, the patient was treated with palliative radiotherapy (3D-CRT) using a 5mm bolus for surface build up (January–February 2026) (Image 3). She achieved significant subjective symptom relief & is disease free when last seen in March 2026.

Image 1: Soft tissue mass with bone destruction

Image 1. Contrast-Enhanced Computed Tomography (CECT) of the Thorax (Dec 2025).

Axial view showing extensive lytic destruction of the manubrium sternum and the medial head of the left clavicle. Note the associated soft tissue attenuation mass causing localized swelling and cortical breach.

Image 2. PET-CT scan showing increased FDG uptake at the lesion in the left sternoclavicular joint.

Visualization of the 3D-CRT treatment volume targeting the left SCJ. A 5mm bolus was applied to the skin surface to ensure adequate dose distribution to the superficial soft tissue component of the metastatic mass.

Isodose Slice View

Elekta
Monaco 6.00.01

English (United States) Format In-use

Hospital/Clinic: _____

Doc Number: Rx A: 19220260202.130014.000

Patient Name: NAVDEEP KAUR

Patient ID: 001RT26

Plan Name: REPLAN:SS_REPLAN:REPLAN

Description: 15Gy/5#

Comment: Width, length, wedge are MONACO values. XYZ positions are in MONACO coordinates. Density overrides used in Monaco calculation. Electron densities are overridden on structures that may be overlapped.

Save Plan Date/Time: _____

Print Date/Time: 4/6/2026 2:18:14 PM

Workstation ID: _____

Plan modified since last Save

MONACO01 192.168.18.211

Slice Location(cm): Transverse: -106.96

Color	Relative (%)
Dark Red	110.00
Red	108.33
Orange-Red	106.67
Orange	105.00
Yellow-Orange	103.33
Yellow	101.67
Light Green	100.00
Green	98.33
Light Blue	96.67
Blue	95.00

100.00 (%) = 1500.0 (cGy)

Color	Structure Name
Red	PTV15Gy/5F7

Image 3: Whole-Body FDG-PET/CT Fusion Imaging (Dec 2025).

The scan demonstrates an intensely FDG-avid lytic lesion at the left sternoclavicular joint and first left costochondral junction. No metabolic activity is noted in the prior right breast surgical site or regional lymph nodes, confirming solitary bone-only recurrence.

Discussion

Solitary sternal or clavicular metastasis is rare, with isolated sternal involvement typically occurring in only 2.4% of bone-only metastases[4]. The contralateral location in this patient suggests a haematogenous route of spread rather than direct lymphatic extension. TNBC exhibits a distinct metastatic pattern; while visceral spread is common, skeletal lesions are predominantly lytic and aggressive, often presenting within 24 months of initial diagnosis [1, 2].

Biopsy of bone lesions remains a diagnostic challenge, with up to 25% of samples being non-diagnostic[5, 6 & 7]. In the setting of high-risk TNBC, functional imaging (PET-CT) is highly sensitive for identifying these early lytic destructions[5]. Palliative radiotherapy remains the gold standard for management, effectively stabilizing bone and providing pain relief in 60–80% of patients [8 & 9].

Conclusion

This case highlights the importance of recognizing the SCJ as a potential site for solitary TNBC metastasis. Early identification of these lesions is crucial for initiating local treatments that maintain quality of life and skeletal integrity.

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